

Chemistry, Chemical Industry and Chemists in India*

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It is customary on the part of the President of the Society to give a brief address at the time of the Annual General Body meeting. It is also customary to make use of this occasion to summarise one's research activities. However, I would like to make a departure from this tradition. I would like to make use of this opportunity to share with you some of my thoughts on certain aspects of chemistry in our country. Accordingly, I have chosen the title; Chemistry, Chemical Industry and Chemists in India. Though, clearly these aspects are interwoven, I feel they are basically distinct enough to permit separate treatment. Furthermore, I would like to point out that the first and the third facets are generic in character and are essential to describe the status of any other discipline and I feel that some of the factors and conclusions to be discussed in the sequel would be equally relevant to many other branches of science in our country.

Chemistry

With all the environmental and ecological problems created by some sections of chemical industry, there can be no two opinions as to the vital role being played by chemistry in the well-being of man and the economy of nations. Nature has bestowed on India several vast and varied material resources, which chemical processing converts or can convert into products for human consumption and comfort. Thus, chemistry has a very vital role to play in upgrading the material life of our people. In this context it appeared worthwhile, first of all, to evaluate the present-day level of this branch of science, in our country.

Growth

Though, the ancient Hindus had achieved contemporary excellence in several chemical processes including metallurgy and pharmaceuticals, and had deeply pondered over the structure of matter¹, chemistry in its modern sense can be considered to be just over 100 years old in India. The first report of a chemical research from India, which attracted the attention of the world community of chemists, concerned the formation of mercurous nitrite and was published in 1896 by P. C. Ray.² Acharya Ray is rightly regarded as the father of chemical research in modern India. His students were mostly responsible for starting research in chemistry at several different centres in

the country.³ By 1924, the volume of research publications from Indian universities was sufficient to encourage Acharya P. C. Ray to found the Indian Chemical Society, with an independent publication organ of its own.³

However, the real fillip to the growth of teaching and research in chemistry, as in other areas, occurred with the independence of the country in 1947. Since then, several new universities and research organizations have been established. At present, as many as 82 universities, out of a total of 117, offer post-graduate teaching in chemistry and it has been estimated that the total M. Sc. output in chemistry was 4157 in 1975 and the number of doctorates (Ph. D/D. Sc) in chemistry turned out during the same period was approximately 500⁴. It has been further estimated⁵ that the 1975 stock (below the age of 60) of post-graduates in chemistry in our country was 54,600, which is almost 11 times the number available in 1950, though during the same period, the population had doubled. The average annual growth rate of this stock during the period 1970-75 has been estimated⁵ to be 12%. The position is very similar in other science disciplines and India is now considered as a country with the third largest number of scientists and technologists in the world, after USA and USSR.

Courses in chemistry cover almost all basic aspects of the discipline and active research is being conducted in several areas of chemistry and chemical technology. It has been recently⁶ estimated that the contribution of Indian chemists to the published literature is of the order of 10% of the total world output. On the basis of these publications, one could further infer that in terms of classical divisions of chemistry, this activity in India is divided very approximately as : theoretical and physical chemistry (19%), inorganic chemistry (45%) and organic chemistry (36%).

From the above growth profile, it is obvious that the Government of India has encouraged the growth of chemistry, like other sciences, in the country. Though it may not be possible to evaluate this in terms of specific financial inputs, a reflection of this can be had by reference to resources being placed at the disposal of scientists and technologists for research and development (R & D), if one

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remembers that approximately 90% of the funds for this expenditure come from the Central and State Governments, and if one accepts the reasonable assumption that the overall chemistry component of all R & D. projects would not decrease with respect to other participating disciplines. The expenditure on R & D has increased from Rs. 29 crores in 1958-59 to Rs. 344.40 crores in 1974-75. The rate of growth during this period has been 18%. In terms of central budget it has increased from 1.61% of the total budget in 1958-59 to 2.57% in 1974-75.⁷

Quality of Research

From the preceding account one cannot escape the conclusion that the growth of chemistry in India has been fairly well-nurtured. If this is so, then immediately some relevant questions confront the mind. How far has this activity helped the country to meet its needs of scientific manpower? How does our performance in research compare with that of other countries?

If we view the first question from a limited angle and not link it up with efficiency/productivity, one can easily conclude that our manpower needs of chemists and chemical engineers have been more than adequately met. As a matter of fact, considering the growth rate of total stock of scientific and technical manpower, which is some three and a half times the rate of growth of corporate employment⁸, the situation calls for urgent corrective measures, if we wish to avoid, what predictably would be a dangerous situation!

The second question—our performance in research—is more profound. Unlike the first question which can be viewed within the social and political constraints of a country, this question cannot be so viewed. Though, there can possibly be local standards for the scientific manpower needed for manning industries, for example, there just cannot be local standards in science. Performance in research can be viewed only from the highest international standards, though the choice of specific areas of endeavour may have been circumscribed by local needs. Research efforts in chemistry, generally fall into one of the two categories: one, research aimed at understanding the structure, reactivity and behaviour of atoms, molecules and grosser matter ('basic research'); and two, efforts geared towards application of this knowledge in developing new products and processes ('applied research'). These two streams often criss-cross and intermingle, yet the objectives remain quite distinct. It will be worthwhile to evaluate our performance in terms of these two categories.

The question which next arises is: how do we evaluate this effort? What parameters to use? Fortunately, this can be done with little ambiguity. Growth of chemistry, as we all know, is studied

with landmarks, some very prominent, some less significant. One has only to recognize, which of these, whether on the trail of theory or methodology or structure, or synthesis owe their genesis to the efforts of Indian chemists, working in India. Though, one can recognize some such landmarks, I am sure, everyone here would agree that the contribution is indeed very meagre, not at all commensurate with either the total volume of publications from India or with its long tradition of enquiry and research.

To evaluate the same matter in a more concrete, though different way would be to have a look at Table 1, which has been constructed from the references cited in Annual Reports of the Chemical Society (London) for three different years, each a decade apart, 1956, 1966 and 1976. If one accepts these citations as a reflection of worthwhile contributions, and which I believe is quite reasonable, and if one disparages any extraneous factors, which some might like to invoke, it is clear from Table 1 that the Indian contribution has been only meagre. What is more disturbing is the fact that relevant citations of Indian origin have decreased over the years (cf. our contributions per 1000 total contributions for the three years). This becomes all the more alarming, when one realises that in recent years⁶ Indian contribution to the published world literature on chemistry has been of the order of some 10%.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF CITATIONS IN ANNUAL REPORTS OF THE CHEMICAL SOCIETY (LONDON) FOR THE YEARS 1956, 1966 AND 1976

Area of Chemistry	1956		1966		1976	
	Total	Indian	Total	Indian	Total	Indian
Theoretical and Physical	969	19	1049	9	522	6
Analytical	825	39	453	5	—	—
Inorganic	418	2	840	8	453	2
Organometallic	—	—	543	1	279	1
Theoretical and Physical organic	260	4	469	0	374	2
Organic	12	24	1377	17	1199	10
Physical methods	365	2	979	11	170	1
Biological	442	5	1067	6	428	2
Total	4545	95	6777	57	3425	24
(base, 1000)	1000	20.5	1000	8.5	1000	7.0

Let us now turn to the second area of research. Unlike, basic research, which is the prime responsibility of universities, the major responsibility for this effort has so far rested on Government-sponsored research laboratories, such as those of

CSIR. Several of these have been in existence for over 20 years and are among the best equipped laboratories, the nation has. Valuable work has been carried out in some of these laboratories by way of working out, usually, known processes for known products and in the utilization of some of our indigenous raw materials. However, if we evaluate the performance in terms of any new catalyst discovered or new products developed or new processes established, I am afraid, again, the performance, at best, can be rated only as very mediocre.

What is wrong ?

If the above conclusions are right, one would like to know what exactly is wrong with our planning and operations, and we are really discussing the period after 1947. One can possibly identify several factors, including those arising from social constraints and political compulsions, but the following four would appear to be over-riding in the present context.

Teaching of chemistry : For many years our curricula were faulty and if now they have been more or less corrected, the implementation of this programme leaves much to be desired. Leaving aside a small percentage of inspired teachers, it would not be wrong to say that in many schools, colleges and universities, the teachers, themselves, have a very superficial knowledge of many subjects, which they are called upon to teach, and hence not only fail to inspire the students, but in fact act as a deterrent ! The spectre of uninspiring teachers has a two-fold origin. Firstly, we have, in general, failed to attract talented people in good numbers to these professions ; reasons for this are not far to seek and shall be discussed in some detail later. Secondly, there has been little effort to organise, in a serious fashion, the continuous education of the teachers. This factor is as vital as the first one, because of the rate at which new information and knowledge is being generated. Poor teachers cannot motivate students and this becomes a chain reaction and the results can be devastating.

Equipment : Practice of chemistry has become more and more instrumentation-based. Not only we need sophisticated spectral and separation equipment for research, but also for teaching, so that the student gets an exposure to these at an early stage in their training. Unfortunately, even now, a majority of our universities are amongst the most ill-equipped. Even our prestigious research institutes do not have instrumentation facilities of the kind, which even an average research institute enjoys in an industrially developed country. This is a serious handicap. Not only this, our timeliness to go in for a particular equipment is lacking. Invariably, one is able to get funds, when the technique has become commonplace elsewhere !

This is partly inherent in the situation as new techniques, and instrumentation have invariably originated and developed abroad. It is true that this is essential because we have to have different priorities and can ill-afford to spare large funds for these, but I feel we have greatly erred by spreading our meagre funds available for the purpose, too thinly. As a corrective measure, the Department of Science and Technology, as well as University Grants Commission have started building up regional sophisticated instrumentation centres.

Direction : Another important factor would be clarity of purpose. Clarity of direction, in the academic sphere, will be reflected in the formulation, continuous up-grading and realigning of the various curricula so as to be consistent with our national aspirations.

Clarity of direction is a pre-requisite for successful R & D activity. I believe, one of the important factors responsible for our poor performance in the area of R & D is the lack of direction. We attempt to do too many things with too little inputs and with scant regard for the expertise of the personnel. It is absolutely essential to lay down a clear direction for the immediate R & D activity of an institute, which should be supported by major inputs so as to reach the objectives in the shortest possible time. Frequent changes in direction have already resulted in much wasted effort. Ad hoc approach must be avoided.

University-Industry Interaction : A crucial factor in the rapid growth of chemistry has been university-industry interaction. This is especially true for Germany. For example, A von Baeyer was awarded the Nobel Prize in Chemistry for 1905—"for his services in the advancement of organic chemistry and chemical industry". The same expression was repeated five years later when O. Wallach won this coveted prize⁹. University-industry interaction is not only mutually beneficial, but is essential to make much of chemistry purposeful. It is only in recent years that the chemical industry in India has shown a healthy growth rate. So far, the university-industry interaction in India has been negligible. This must be strengthened.

Chemical Industry

As an obvious extension of what we have been talking about would be to have a look at our chemical industry as well. Chemical industry is the only tangible link between chemistry and the people at large. As already stated a healthy chemical industry is one of the prerequisites for the sustained growth of chemistry itself.

The indigenous chemical industry, in the modern sense, can be considered to have taken birth in 1901, when Acharya P. C. Ray became instrumental in the setting up of a pharmaceutical unit around Calcutta.

A few years later, Rajmitra B. D. Amin started another similar unit in Baroda. However, the growth of this industry remained poor due to various economic and political reasons, and it is only after 1947, that a healthy growth rate has emerged. The total turnover of chemicals has increased from some 60 crores in 1950 to over Rs. 2,200 crores in 1974. The capital base of the industry has expanded from about Rs. 304 crores in 1961 to Rs. 2,200 crores in 1974¹⁰. During the last decade, its overall growth rate has been around 13-14% which compares very favourably with that of industrially advanced countries (Table 2) and is significantly higher than that of other manufacturing industries. Chemical industry in India now ranks fourth after textiles, iron and steel, and engineering. There are over 700 units¹⁰ in the medium- and large-scale sectors and the variety of chemicals produced scans a wide spectrum. The export of chemicals and products based on them has steadily increased from Rs. 14.25 crores in 1963-64 to Rs. 164.28 crores in 1976-1977¹¹.

Thus, we see, Indian chemical industry has made very impressive strides in recent years. However, we have still a long way to go. Our

TABLE 2—AVERAGE ANNUAL GROWTH RATE (%) FOR THE PERIOD: 1968-1978

Country	Average annual growth rate (%)	
	Chemicals	All manufacturing
Britain	8.1	4.3
France	10.8	6.1
Germany	10.8	6.1
Japan	11.5	12.3
U. S. A	8.1	4.3
India	13.2	6.8

Source : O. P. Kharbanda, "Process Plant and Equipment Cost Estimation", Sevak Publications, Bombay, 1977, p. 17

import of chemicals is still very large : Rs. 450 crores for 1976-77 (Table 3). The turnover of the Indian chemical industry even in 1974 was less than 1% of the total world chemicals production (Table 4). The cost of most of chemicals in India is much higher, often two or three times, than the prevailing international prices¹².

• Since India has a huge internal market, the potential for the growth of the chemical industry is indeed immense. We must utilise this opportunity for an ordered growth, a growth which is at once compatible with the environment and our socio-economic goals. We are fortunately placed to learn from the mistakes of the industrialised world and

must avoid these and take all steps to contain pollution and ecological damage. Already, in several places a lot of damage has been done. We must acquire the best technology and, productivity should not be sacrificed. In the name of self-sufficiency, inefficiency should not be cultivated. We must build indigenous capability and to that effect, the chemical industry, which has a high rate of obsolescence, must generously invest in R & D. The chemical industry must help the growth of chemistry at the universities, which would be its investment for innovation and sustained competitive growth. A recent U. S survey¹³ revealed that 52% of all inventors hold Ph. D degree.

TABLE 3—IMPORTS OF CHEMICALS AND PRODUCTS BASED ON CHEMICALS (Rupees in Crores)

Groups	1975-76	1976-77
1 Organic chemicals	134.32	88.73
2 Inorganic chemicals	45.88	48.48
3 Crude chemicals from Coal, Petroleum, etc.	0.45	1.18
4 Dyeing and tanning materials	11.82	15.09
5 Medicinal and pharmaceutical products	36.26	42.14
6 Essential oils, perfumery materials, etc.	2.14	2.21
7 Fertilizers	469.41	197.72
8 Explosives, etc.	0.58	0.33
9 Plastics, resins, etc.	19.54	27.35
10 Chemical materials and products, n.e.s.	39.49	26.33
Total	759.89	449.56

Ref. Monthly Statistics of Foreign Trade of India, Vol. II, Imports, Govt. of India, March 1977.

Chemist

I think we have talked enough about chemistry and chemical industry. It is time now to give some thought to the man, who has made chemistry his profession and life's ambition—the CHEMIST. In any successful endeavour, man is the key-factor : if he is motivated, has job satisfaction, has congenial working conditions and no unusual family and social constraints, he is bound to be effective. We assemble here, to-day, as chemists, and I think in the context of today's topic, it will be worthwhile to evaluate his status (in the society), his professional risks and hazards.

The job of a practising chemist is potentially hazardous, but more so in our country, where provision of safety practice monitoring, whether in the college or in the university or in the factory is practically non-existent. One has only to visit an

TABLE 4—ANNUAL TURNOVER OF WORLD CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES (in US \$)

Region	1964		1974		Population, crores (1974)
	\$ crores	%	\$ crores	%	
1 Western Europe (OECD)	2,820	29.9	10,400	32.0	40.0
2 U. S. A. + Canada	3,360	35.6	8,200	26.0	23.4
3 USSR + Eastern Europe (CMEA)	1,740	18.5	7,000	22.0	36.0
4 Japan	520	5.5	3,300	10.0	11.0
5 India	70	0.7	280	0.9	58.0
6 All others (except China)	910	9.8	2,820	9.1	148.0
World total	9,420	100.0	32,000	100.0	316.4

Sources : R. MALPAS, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1977, 886W. E. CAWLEY, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1976, 284

Ref. 10

undergraduate practicals class in a college or a small or medium- or large-scale chemical plant, to convince himself. For this plight, the chemist himself is responsible to some extent, but mostly he has no option. A recent survey (USA) revealed a significantly higher frequency of occurrence of cancer amongst the practising chemists. The chemist in the academia, like his counterparts in other disciplines of science, is, these days, up against the almost impossible task of keeping abreast of the latest developments even in his own narrow field of specialization. Unlike the situation in many other, so-called non-science disciplines, a scientist, during the course of his career is evaluated and re-evaluated in terms of what he has achieved and how much knowledge of the latest developments does he possess. Thus, a chemist (and in general a scientist) has to work extra hard to remain viable.

If this is so, why do people take up chemistry or, science in general, as a profession? May be because of better emoluments; let us deal with this first. A 1971 survey, carried out in India gives some revealing data! In general, scientists receive lower starting salaries than their counterparts in the engineering professions. Career advancement with age is much slower for the scientists. It has been estimated that the salary level reached by the scientists at 55 years of age, is reached by the administrators at 40. Even the proportion of positions in the higher ranges is much smaller for the scientists. For example, it is revealed that in the National Laboratories, scientists with the salary of Rs. 2000 or more constitute some 2% compared to about 20% in the case of administrators. Similarly, scientists with Rs. 1300-2000 constitute about 18% compared to 30% among the administrators. The salaries of chemists in some small- and medium-scale industries are deplorably low.

Thus, better emoluments is certainly not a factor. Would it be higher prestige associated with being a scientist? Again, this is not true. Compare the level of awards designed to recognise talent in science with similar awards for cultural fields.

Then, why do people go in for chemistry or any other science? It was the lure of the unknown, the romance of discovery, the thrill of unlocking the secrets of nature! But, things have changed fast. The newer generations are more pragmatic. Science no longer draws the best brains. Students prefer professions which are more remunerative: engineering, medicine, business, administration, accountancy. This trend has been clearly revealed in a recent survey on 'Science Education', conducted on behalf of National Council for Science and Technology. Not only this, according to UGC estimates, the enrolment in science faculty for 1975-76 was only 4,64,000 compared to the figure 9,15,000 for 1969-70. This is an alarming situation.

The Government of India Scientific Policy Resolution (1958), states among other things: "... to ensure an adequate supply, within the country, of research scientists of highest quality...". If this is so, it is still not too late to take corrective measures so that some of the best talents can be attracted to science. For this, the chemist's/scientist's job will have to be made more remunerative, his working conditions improved, minimum level of salaries for different basic qualifications will have to be fixed to avoid exploitation, some system to reward innovation will have to be found as is being done in countries like France. The Indian Chemical Society and other professional organizations can help, provided they can overcome the existing grooves.

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